

INVESTIGATIONS ON THE ULTIMATE COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH GEOMETRICAL IMPERFECTIONS

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SUMMARY

A series of studies has been performed within the MARSTRUCT Network of Excellence on Marine Structures in order to investigate the buckling response of glass fibre reinforced polymer plates. These studies include the fabrication, testing and finite element analysis of a large number of plates with initial geometric imperfections. This paper presents the validation of finite element models against a series of plate tests that were performed within this framework and parametric studies that were carried out to identify the effects of geometric imperfections on the ultimate compressive strength of composite plates with three alternative lay-up configurations.

Keywords: GFRP, post-buckling strength, geometric imperfections, progressive failure.

INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials for the fabrication of primary and secondary structural members is continuously increasing in the marine and offshore industries. Examples of their application include ship hull construction, lightweight superstructures for ships and offshore platforms and wind turbine blades. The most common material used in these applications is E-glass fibre reinforcement due to its low cost and high strength characteristics.

In contrast to steel and aluminium structures, large uncertainty exists in the design of panels made from composite materials due to limited information available. Strength design curves under in-plane compressive loads have been well established for their homogeneous counterparts and take into account geometric imperfection effects, lack of experimental data for composite panels in compression has driven the design of these structures to be limited to their critical buckling loads. Scarcity of information on manufacturing defects increases the level of uncertainty which is normally dealt with by additional knock-down factors being introduced in the design of these structures.

In an attempt to provide a set of design curves for composite panels for marine and offshore applications, a wide range of studies has been carried out within MARSTRUCT – Network of Excellence on Marine Structures. These studies consisted of a large number of compressive tests on square glass-epoxy composite plates [1], round-robin material characterisation tests [2] and non-linear finite element analysis (FEA) in Abaqus/CAE for parametric studies on plates in compression including the validation of the numerical models [3]. An overview of this work and a preliminary parametric study on the ultimate compressive strength of square composite plates has been presented in Ref. [4].

The majority of the numerical solutions for the validation of the finite element models showed good correlation with the experimental results. In early pilot tests [5] it was established that panel edge displacements and rotations from digital image correlation (DIC) measurements must be applied in the analysis to achieve a correct panel response; the same approach was followed in the present analyses. The section response is calculated based on first order shear deformation theory and a progressive failure model with the Hashin failure criteria [6] and recursive degradation of the material properties. Some issues related to the rigidity of the supports for the thick plate tests, identified the need for further investigations with regards to the numerical approach.

This paper focuses on the finite element analysis performed for the parametric studies and the validation of the numerical models. The latter are extended with analysis performed in ANSYS with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion [7] and instantaneous degradation of the material properties for the propagation of damage. By comparing the two progressive failure models the level of uncertainty in the numerical approach is reduced and allows for parametric studies to be conducted.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Plate specimens for three panel series were produced at NTUA (Series 1 and 2) and by Vestas Wind Systems A/S on behalf of DTU (Series 3). The composite systems used by the two fabricators were similar but not identical, and the production methods followed were also different.

The DTU material was a pre-preg E-glass fibre/epoxy system. The fibre reinforcement comprised two types of E-glass fabrics: a 1200 g/m² UD fabric and a 600 g/m² ±45° biaxial, knitted, non-crimp fabric. The NTUA material was a wet lay-up E-glass/epoxy system. The fibre reinforcement comprised a 623 g/m² UD glass fabric (with 50 g/m² in weft direction) together with a 306 g/m² ±45° biaxial non-crimp fabric, and an epoxy resin with low viscosity (600-750 mPa.s at 25°C). The averaged property definitions as derived from round-robin material characterisation tests performed at NTUA and DTU are presented in Table 1.

With UD representing the unidirectional layers and by BIAX the biaxial layers, the lay-ups of the three series are the following:

- Series 1: [BIAX / 4xUD / BIAX / 3xUD]_s
- Series 2: [BIAX / 4xUD / BIAX / 4xUD / BIAX / 3xUD]_s
- Series 3: [BIAX / 4xUD / BIAX / 3xUD / BIAX / 2xUD]_s

All lay-ups are symmetrical, and the weight of the UD layers is 88% for Series 1 and 2 and 87% for Series 3. The thicknesses of most specimens were measured using a 3-D contact digitiser, and the nominal thicknesses of Series 1-3 were approximately 9, 15 and 20 mm respectively.

Series 3 plates had a width-to-thickness ratio (b/t) such that the elastic critical load and the load for compressive fibre failure over a complete section would be approximately equal, giving the maximum sensitivity to initial geometric imperfections; the remaining two groups had medium to high width-to-thickness ratios.

Table 1. Average material properties from NTUA and DTU tests (in MPa).

Property	NTUA material		DTU material	
	NTUA test	DTU test	NTUA test	DTU test
E_{1t}	29658	33170	48634	56235
E_{1c}	38671	37238	50619	56209
E_{2t}	6563	9338	18535	20422
E_{2c}	8501	9536	12325	15729
G_{12}	2034	2169	4800	4264
ν_{12}	0.290	0.268	0.274	0.284
X_t	559	698	968	1141
X_c	253	191	915	952
Y_t	60	43	24	22
Y_c	59	69	118	127
S	31	30	65	64

Each plate had a nominal total length (L) of 400 mm (parallel to the load direction) and width (B) of 380 mm (Fig. 1). When the plate was mounted in the test fixture, its unsupported length (a) and width (b) were both 320 mm (Fig. 1). Each of the three plate series comprised 9 plates. Three of these plates were perfectly plane, three had a small maximum imperfection and the remaining three had a large maximum imperfection. The values of the imperfection amplitudes (δ_o) were defined as a function of the unsupported width of the plate ($\delta_o / b = 0.01$ and 0.03) resulting in maximum imperfections of 3.2 and 9.6 mm.

The shape of the geometric imperfection was a scaled first buckling mode-shape of a corresponding fully clamped plate with dimensions $a' = b' = 300$ mm (Fig. 1). This left a 10 mm wide plane strip near the plate's clamped edges, in order to ensure easy fitting into the test fixture. A digital image correlation (DIC) measurement system was used alongside conventional strain gauges and displacement transducers to monitor plate deformations. The tests indicated significant reductions of the plate failure load when imperfections are present.

Figure 1. Geometry of the test plates (top-left), shape of geometric imperfections (bottom-left), test rig (top-right) and actual plate boundary conditions (bottom-right).

VALIDATION OF FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

The full set of comparisons for the validation study has been presented in Ref. [3, 4] where it was concluded that a number of issues required further investigation. This section presents the extension of this study with alternative modelling approaches. The results from the full set of the validation study are also presented here in tabular format for completeness.

The majority of the FE analysis for these studies has been performed in Abaqus/CAE with the Hashin (1973) failure criteria and a rate-dependent, linear degradation of the material properties for the propagation of damage. Eight-node degenerated shell elements were adopted in the FE discretizations (type S8R in Abaqus) which represent thick shells; first order shear deformation theory is implemented in the element formulation to accommodate transverse shear effects. The averaged material property definitions from the NTUA tests were incorporated in the FE model and transverse isotropy was assumed for the remaining property definitions.

Due to significant deformations of the panel supports being observed during the tests the edges of the plates were modelled with simply supported and clamped boundary conditions to try and band the experimental results. This has been achieved in most cases except for the thick panels (Series 3). The unsupported area of the plates ($a \times b$) was discretized with a 46×46 mesh according to the results of a mesh refinement study with the Series 3 geometrically imperfect model until the convergence of the solutions had been met.

For the cases where the nonlinear boundary conditions from the DIC measurements are imposed, only the geometrically imperfect area ($a' \times b'$ in Fig. 1) was modelled. Here the

same mesh refinement was used as in the clamped and simply supported cases. The edges of the FE models were divided into sets of master nodes, where the measured 3-D displacements and the rotations about the axis parallel to each edge were applied, and slave nodes. The displacements and rotations of each set of slave nodes were linearly interpolated from the adjacent master nodes. In most cases, the combination of the progressive failure model with the application of the non-linear boundary conditions caused localised failure at the master nodes which significantly reduced the load-carrying capability of the model. For this reason the FE models with boundary nonlinearities include only the geometrically nonlinear effects and the progressive failure model has been removed from the analysis.

Additional theoretical results are presented from modelling carried out in ANSYS with the nonlinear boundary conditions implemented. The two displacement degrees of freedom in the axis normal to each edge were applied to the master nodes and the remaining four degrees of freedom at the nodes were kept free. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion was adopted to identify the initiation of failure and a progressive failure model was implemented in the code with instantaneous degradation of the material properties. Validation and detailed description of this failure model has been presented in Ref. [8]. To improve computational efficiency these models were discretized with a 30×30 mesh of 4-node, shear deformable degenerated shell elements. The averaged material property definitions from the DTU tests were incorporated in these models.

Table 2. FEA correlation with panel tests (failure stresses in MPa, deviations in %).

Panel	Test	FEA – CC*		FEA – SS*		FEA – NonLinear**	
	MPa	MPa	Dev %	MPa	Dev %	MPa	Dev %
S1-0-2	115	123	6.96	105	-8.70	80	-30.61
S1-32-2	106	111	4.72	104	-1.89	70	-34.15
S1-96-1	91	103	13.19	88	-3.30	65	-28.46
S2-0-2	183	184	0.55	113	-38.25	170	-7.21
S2-32-2	149	148	-0.67	113	-24.16	111	-25.70
S2-96-2	133	133	0.00	107	-19.55	96	-27.52
S3-0-2	287	517	80.14	289	0.70	385	33.97
S3-96-1	218	382	75.23	277	27.06	158	-27.52

* Clamped/Simply Supported boundary conditions with the Hashin failure criteria.

** Non-linear boundary conditions (rotations free) with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion.

The correlations between the numerical solutions and the experimental results are presented in Table 2 for the simply supported and clamped models with the Hashin failure criteria and for the models with the non-linear boundary conditions imposed with the Tsai-Wu criterion. Good correlation between the test results of the medium thickness panels (Series 2) and the FE models with clamped edges is presented in terms of their collapse loads and also with their curves of load against end shortening. Only a typical set of these curves is presented here (Fig. 2) due to limitations of available space.

Figure 2 demonstrates typical examples of the problems encountered during this validation study. Series 1 panels, with and without initial geometric imperfections, performed in a similar manner to that presented for the largest maximum imperfection of 9.6 mm. The initial in-plane stiffness of the panels was modelled accurately with the clamped boundary conditions, however, due to the low bending stiffness of the thin plates, large out-of-plane displacements exhibited by these panels caused early damage at the edges that was not predicted in the analysis. All Series 1 panels failed between the clamped and simply supported predictions as presented in Table 2.

Figure 2. Load – End shortening curves and buckling loads for panels Series 1 and Series 2 with 9.6 mm maximum initial imperfections (top) and for panels Series 3 with and without initial imperfections (bottom).

The nonlinear boundary conditions imposed in these models have been taken from DIC measurements of a smaller panel area ($a' \times b'$) as described earlier and include any additional out of plane displacements and rotations resulting from the early damage at

the edges. Therefore, the solutions with these boundary conditions (but without material failure) show good convergence with the experimental results. The numerical solutions from ANSYS with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion present an initial stiffness of the models identical to the simply supported cases since the rotational degrees of freedom are kept free. These boundary conditions were used in order to avoid premature failure of the material associated with the master nodes. Even though this problem has been greatly reduced it is not eliminated. The linearly interpolated displacements of the slave nodes cause discontinuities on the edge surfaces which result in high localised stresses occurring at the master nodes and hence, premature failure of their neighbouring elements. The stiffness of the FE models is then reduced (Fig. 2) and the predicted ultimate loads are, in most cases, significantly lower than in the test results (Table 2).

The thick plates in Series 3 have higher stiffness properties than Series 1 and 2 panels and caused large deformations of the supports during testing which affected considerably the results. The plate with no initial geometric imperfection imposed (S3-0-2) performed as in the simply supported case (Fig. 2). The plate with large initial imperfection (S3-96-1) demonstrated an in-plane stiffness as in the clamped FE model but failed very early during testing. Even though the non-linear boundary conditions assisted in the modelling of these panels, no conclusions have been derived until now on their collapse. These investigations are still in progress with more detailed modelling of the boundary conditions and alternative failure models.

PARAMETRIC STUDIES

A parametric study to investigate the effect of initial imperfections on the strength of composite panels is presented in this section. The parametric study incorporates three lay-up configurations for two plate geometries: an aspect ratio of 1 (square plates) and an aspect ratio of 4 (long plates), with the width (b) of the panels being set to 500 mm in all cases.

The three lay-up configurations are presented in Table 3. Cases A and B consist of unidirectional plies and case C incorporates woven roving (WR) materials. Cases B and C provide balanced laminate properties; in order to avoid resemblance in the numerical solutions the woven roving lay-up was modelled to consist of balanced plies. In the triaxial lay-up (case A) the thicknesses for each layer are scaled up to achieve the desired plate thickness and slenderness. In the other two lay-up configurations (quadriaxial and woven roving) increased thickness is achieved by increasing the number of plies (n).

Table 3. Definition of lay-up configurations.

Case A:	$[-45/+45/0_4/+45/-45/0_4/-45/+45/0_3]_s$
Case B:	$[0/+45/90/-45]_{n,s}$
Case C:	$[0]_n$

The imposed imperfections for the square plates have a half sine-wave form with amplitudes of 0.1%, 1%, 2% and 3% of the panel width. The imperfection shape of the long plates is a combined imperfection of 20% the preferred buckling mode shape of each panel and 80% of a half sine-wave which has resulted from an investigation on the effect of the imperfection shape on the ultimate strength of these panels and provides a more realistic imperfection for the FE models. The preferred buckling mode for case A has 3 half waves in the longitudinal direction whereas, cases B and C have 4.

The material property definitions for the first two cases are the same as NTUA data set for the DTU material (Table 1). For the woven roving material (WR), properties have been adapted from an earlier study [9] and are provided in Table 4.

Table 4. WR material properties (MPa).

E_1	17180	ν_{12}	0.17	G_{12}	3520
E_2	17180	ν_{13}	0.27	G_{13}	5150
E_3	10800	ν_{23}	0.27	G_{23}	5150
X_t	238.6	Y_t	238.6	S_{12}	80.9
X_c	324.5	Y_c	324.5	S_{23}	60.7

For the purposes of the parametric study, the FEA model had some of its features altered. By examining the first buckling mode shapes for all configurations it was concluded that half symmetry would be applied about an axis parallel to the panel's length. To simulate the effect of surrounding structure (stiffeners and adjacent panels) the unloaded edge was constrained to remain straight but free to displace in the y-direction with the rotations being kept free as in the simply supported case. The mesh of the square plates consists of the same size of elements as in the validation study. A mesh refinement study was repeated for the long plates which resulted in a 100×13 mesh.

Figure 3 presents the ultimate strength (MPa) for a wide range of b/t values for the square (left) and long (right) plates for the three lay-up configurations considered (top to bottom). For the square plates, initial imperfection effects are small for b/t values greater than 25 but become significant in the lower range of b/t.

The long plates appear in general to be less affected by the imperfections compared to the square panels. The effects are again small for b/t values greater than 25 (or 30 for case C) but in the lower range these effects appear to be constant for the WR (case C) and quadriaxial (case B) lay-ups with the triaxial (case A) lay-up showing significant differences only in the lowest range (b/t less than 10). The similarities between cases B and C are due to the balanced properties in the longitudinal and transverse directions. Any anomalies in these curves at b/t in the range of 20-30 are due to a change of the failure mode.

Figure 3. Effect of initial geometric imperfections on the ultimate compressive strength of square (left) and long (right) plates for alternative lay-up configurations (cases A-C).

CONCLUSIONS

A series of studies for the investigation of the compressive strength of composite plates has been presented. The studies consist of the validation of FE models against a series of glass reinforced polymer plates tested with and without initial geometric imperfections imposed, and a set of parametric studies to identify the effects of initial imperfections on the compressive strength of composite panels with alternative lay-up configurations.

The validation study demonstrated good correlation between the experimental and numerical results for the medium thickness panels (Series 2) whereas further investigations must take place for the thin (Series 1) and thick (Series 3) panels. These should consider alternative failure criteria and boundary conditions of the panels, especially for the thick panels where a large influence from the deformations of the test rig was identified.

The parametric studies demonstrated a large influence on the compressive strength from initial geometric imperfections in the lower b/t regions (less than 25) and for all lay-up configurations. Compared to square plates, the effect from imperfections is in general reduced in the long plates and does not seem to vary significantly as the b/t value is reduced. In the high slenderness region these effects are minimised for all lay-up configurations.

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